

OPTIMIZATION OF PEB STRUCTURE UNDER SEISMIC FORCE WITH VARIOUS BRACING PATTERN

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Abstract

The optimization of Pre-Engineered Building (PEB) structures under seismic forces, considering various bracing patterns, offers critical insights into their structural behavior and seismic performance. This study conducts a comprehensive analysis of different bracing configurations, evaluating parameters such as storey displacement, axial force, bending moment, shear force, time period, and frequency response. The findings reveal significant variations across these parameters, influenced by the bracing pattern and seismic zone, specifically Zones II and IV. In Zone IV, characterized by higher seismic activity, the study observes elevated values across all parameters compared to Zone II. Among the various bracing patterns analyzed, X bracing consistently emerges as a superior strategy. It demonstrates effective performance in reducing storey displacement, axial force, bending moment, shear force, and time period, thereby enhancing the overall seismic resilience of PEB structures. This robust performance underscores X bracing's potential as a reliable seismic retrofitting approach. The research highlights the critical role of tailored bracing strategies, considering the specific structural requirements and geographical seismic risks. While X bracing shows promising results, its efficacy can vary depending on the building design and seismic zone. Thus, the study advocates for customized seismic retrofitting solutions to optimize structural performance and safety. In conclusion, the analysis underscores the importance of selecting appropriate bracing configurations to mitigate seismic impacts effectively. The superior performance of X bracing across multiple seismic parameters in both Zone II and IV suggests its broad applicability. However, the necessity for further research is evident, aimed at refining bracing designs to enhance seismic resilience across diverse building typologies and regions. These findings provide a foundation for future efforts in developing optimized seismic retrofitting strategies, ensuring the structural integrity and safety of PEB structures in various seismic conditions.

Keywords- *PEB Structures, Seismic Forces, Bracing Patterns, Structural Behavior, Seismic Performance, X Bracing, Seismic Retrofitting, Dynamic Analysis.*

I. Introduction

Pre-engineered buildings (PEB) have become a preferred choice in construction due to their cost-effectiveness, quick assembly, and flexibility. However, optimizing PEB structures to withstand seismic forces is crucial for ensuring safety and structural integrity, especially in earthquake-prone regions. This study focuses on the optimization of PEB structures under seismic loads by evaluating different bracing patterns configurations. Bracing patterns, such as X-bracing, V-bracing, and K-bracing, play a significant role in enhancing the lateral stiffness and stability of structures. Additionally, the selection and design of joints influence the overall behavior of PEB structures during seismic events. By analyzing various combinations of bracing patterns, this research aims to identify the most effective configurations for minimizing seismic impact.

The optimization process involves rigorous computational simulations and experimental validations to assess the performance of each bracing pattern under different seismic conditions. Advanced finite element analysis (FEA) tools will be employed to model the dynamic response of PEB structures,

considering factors such as material properties, load distributions, and boundary conditions. The study will also explore the cost implications and practical feasibility of implementing these optimized configurations in real-world construction projects.

1.1 Concept of PEB

"Pre-engineered steel buildings" are those which are fully fabricated in the factory after designing, shipped to site in CKD (completely knocked down) condition; and all components are assembled and erected at site with nut-bolts, thereby reducing the time of completion. Pre-engineered means, generally speaking, is any part of a structure that is manufactured firstly to its arrival on the building site. The concept of the Pre-Engineered Building (PEB) is one where the fabrication is completed in a controlled environment with the recent technology, and then after erection is carried out. Though initially only off the shelf products were available in these configurations dependent by the technological development tailor made solutions are also made using this technology in very small durations. The designs were ready-made but the building components were either ready-made or manufactured against specific orders. These buildings were pre-designed or 'pre-engineered' into standard sizes, spans, bays and heights, and use standard details for fixing cladding, roofing, gutters, flashing, windows, doors taking advantage of industrial practices of mass production of components economically. Although PEB systems are extensively used in industrial and many other non-residential constructions worldwide, it is relatively a new concept in India. These concepts were introduced to the India in the late 1990's with the opening up of the economy; and a number of multi-nationals setting up their projects. The current pre-engineered steel building manufacturing capacity is 6.0 lac ton per annum. The industry is growing at the compound rate of 25 to 30%. With respect to design of the structure and aesthetic appearance India is way behind. Indian manufacturers are trying to catch up; comparatively PEB is a new concept in India. A healthy trend in the form of growth in demand for construction works in residential, Commercial, Institutional industrial and infrastructure sectors are being seen over the past decade. Modern Structures are much more complex and staggery as compared to earlier period. One of the major changes which are being felt by all is that the present structures are taller and thinner. Latest day requirement of structures is that these should be lighter yet not compromising on functionality. Civil engineering construction has seen a continuous economic competition between steel, concrete and other construction materials. Currently, the total steel production in the country is about 45 MN Ton against 1280 MN ton of world. Per capita steel consumption in India is 42 kg whereas it is 270 kg in China. About 10% of steel goes to the construction industry and amidst it PEB accounts only for the 0.5 MN ton as on date. In the next 5 years, the steel production will be doubled and with efforts of organizations like BIS and INSDAG, steel intensive construction may rise up to 22 MN ton. Owing to advantages of PEB, separate nonconventional segments are also getting attracted to use PEB and the potential will rise up to 2.2 MN ton which is four to five times of today's scenario. Subsequent paragraphs are only a humble attempt to present the various aspects of immaterial development, technology of design and manufacture; and future growth aspects of Pre-engineered building Industry in India along with its grey areas.

1.2 Classification of Steel Buildings

Steel is the material of choice for design because it is inherently ductile and flexible. It flexes under hyper loads rather than crushing and crumbling. Structural steels low cost, strength, durability, design flexibility, adaptability and recyclability continue to make it the material of choice in building construction. Today's structural steel framing is bringing grace, art and function together in almost limitless ways and is offering new solutions and opportunities to create challenging structures, which

were once thought impossible. Steel structures have reserve strength. Simple stick design in the steel framings allows construction to proceed rapidly from the start of erection.

1.2.1 Conventional Steel Buildings

Conventional Steel buildings are consultant and conservative. The Structural members are hot rolled and are used in conventional buildings. The materials are produced or manufactured in the plant and are shifted to the site. The raw materials are processed in the site for the desired form and erected. The modifications can be done during erection by cut and weld process. Truss systems are used in conventional system.

Fig 1: Conventional Steel Frame

(ref. paper- Comparative study of pre-engineered steel structure by varying width of structure, IJAET E-ISSN 0976-3945)

1.2.2 Pre Engineered Steel Buildings

Pre Engineered Steel Buildings are manufactured or Produced in the plant itself. The manufacturing of structural members is done on customer requirements. The detailed structural members are designed for their respective location and are numbered, which cannot be altered; because members are manufactured with respect to design features. These components are made in modular or completely knocked condition for transportation. These materials are transported to the customer site and are erected. Welding and cutting process are not performed at the customer site. No manufacturing process done at the customer site.

Fig 1: Pre-Engineered Steel Frames

(ref. paper- Comparative study of pre-engineered steel Structure by varying width of structure, IJAET E-ISSN 0976-3945)

1.3 Pre-engineered steel building implementation as Industrial Sheds

India being a developed country grand house building construction is taking place in various parts of the country. Since 30% of Indian population lives in towns and cities; hence construction is more in the urban places. The requirement of housing is higher but there will always be a shortage of house availability as the present masonry construction technology cannot meet the rising demand every year. Hence one has to think for alternative construction system for steel or timber buildings, but timber is anyway not suitable to tropical countries like India. In structural engineering, a pre-engineered building (PEB) is designed by a manufacturer to be fabricated using a pre-determined inventory of raw materials and manufacturing methods that can efficiently satisfy a wide range of structural and aesthetic design requirements. Within some geographic industry sectors these buildings are also called Pre-Engineered Metal Buildings. Historically, the primary framing structure of a Pre Engineered Building is an assembly of I-shaped members, often referred as I-beam. In PEB, I section beams used are usually formed by welding together steel plates to form of I section. I section beams are then field-assembled (e.g. Bolted connections) to form the entire frame of the Pre-Engineered Building. Cold formed Z and C-shaped members may be used as secondary structural elements to fasten and support the external cladding. Roll-formed profiled steel sheet, wood, tensioned fabric, precast concrete, masonry block, glass curtain wall or other materials may be used for the external cladding of the building. In order to accurately design a pre-engineered building, engineers consider the clear span between bearing points, bay spacing, roof slope, live loads, dead loads, collateral loads, wind uplift, deflection criteria, internal crane system and maximum practical size and weight of fabricated members.

In pre-engineered building concept the complete designing is done at the factory and the building components are brought to the site in CKD (Completely knock down condition). These components are then fixed / jointed at the site and raised with the help of cranes. The Pre-Engineered Building calls for very fast construction of buildings and with good aesthetic looks and quality construction. Pre-Engineered Buildings can be used extensively for construction of industrial and residential buildings. The buildings can be multi storied (4-6 floors). These buildings are suitable to various environmental hazards. Pre-Engineered Buildings can be adapted to suit a wide variety of structural applications; the greatest economy will be realized when utilizing standard details. An efficiently designed pre-engineered building can be lighter than the conventional steel buildings by up to 30%. Lighter weight equates to less steel and a potential price savings in structural framework.

1.5 Components of PEB

Main Framing

Fig 2: Typical PEB Steel structure

(Ref Paper- Design and Analysis of Pre Engineered Steel Frame, IJRSAE, Oct-Dec- 2014)

Main framing basically includes the rigid steel frames of the building. The PEB rigid frame comprises tapered/straight columns and tapered rafters (steel plate fabricated 'I' or 'H' sections are referred to as built-up members). The frame is erected by bolting the end plates of connecting sections together.

Secondary frame or Purlins, girts etc.

Purlins, girts and eave struts are also known as secondary cold-formed members. There is no welding involved in their preparation. They are prepared by press bending the HR steel coil giving it the desired shape (Z- or C-shape).

Roof & Wall Panels

Metallic plain or colour coated profiled steel sheets are used as roof and wall sheeting. The steel sheets are generally made from Zinalume or Galvalume coils in thickness range of 0.47 mm to 0.55 mm. The base steel is either galvanized having a zinc coating varying from a minimum Mass of 120 gsm./m² to a maximum of 275 gsm./m² (total of both sides) or a base steel coating of zinc – aluminium (zinc 45%, aluminium 55%) of total Mass of 150 gsm./m² (total of both sides) are available with permanent colour coating. The colour coating is also available in various options in polyester paint coating like regular modified polyester, silicon modified polyester and super polyester coatings.

Insulations

These buildings can be properly insulated by providing fibrous insulation slabs/rolls of non-combustible Rockwool, Aluminium foil laminated, placed over a metal mesh bed created between the Purlins, and then the roofing steel sheet fixed over it. The siding walls can also be insulated by providing a double skin profile steel sheet wall cladding having Rockwool Insulation slab sandwiched in between and held in position with the help of 'Z' spacers in between the two profile steel sheets. In similar pattern a double skin insulated roofing system can also be erected.

Sandwich Panels

Another alternative is to provide pre-fabricated insulated panels, which comprises two single skin panels (plain steel sheets Zinalume colour coated) with polyurethane foam insulation in between. These panels are intended for use as thermally efficient roof and wall claddings for buildings e.g. in high altitude areas and cold storages. In addition to the above sandwich panels also find extensive use in residential as well as non-residential buildings. The panels provide sufficient

insulation and noise reduction properties. Nowadays large cold storage units (Potato, Onion, vegetables, processed foods etc.) are also made with this Pre Engineered Building technique.

Mezzanine systems

Standard mezzanine structure consists of built-up beams that support built-up, hot-rolled or cold-formed mezzanine joists which in-turn support a metal deck. A concrete slab is cast on the metal deck as a finished surface. Steel checker plates may also be used as top surface. These mezzanines are used for office space, storage or equipment supports in industries. For commercial buildings and high rise structures several types of light weight panel boards are available as horizontal surface. The primary mezzanine beams should run across the width of the building parallel to the main frame rafters. Joist should run parallel to the roof pultrins along the length of the building.

Fig 3: Mezzanine systems

Bracing system

Longitudinal cross bracing, used to provide lateral stability to the structure against wind, seismic or other forces, comprises of rods, pipes, angles or cables with an eye bolt and an adjusting nut at both ends, located near the outer flange of columns or rafters and attached at the web of the rigid frame. It is important to trace the longitudinal crane forces through the structure in order to insure proper wall and crane bracing. For lightly loaded cranes, wind bracing in the plane of the wall may be adequate for resisting longitudinal crane forces. While for every large longitudinal forces, the bracing is most likely to be required in the plane of crane rail.

Fig 4: PEB Bracing System

II. Literature Review

Sapkale Nikhil P (2017) focuses on the numerical analysis of Pre-Engineered Buildings (PEB) industrial shed trusses under accidental loads using STAAD Pro V8i, comparing PEB with Conventional Steel Buildings (CSB). Designed according to IS: 800-2007 and analyzed per IS: 875-1987, the research highlights PEB's cost and time efficiency over CSB. Hemant Sharma (2017) further compares PEB and CSB, emphasizing the analysis of bending moments in various sections and the design of structural components like purlins and bracings for a location in Vadodara, Gujarat. His findings support PEB's economic and time-saving benefits. Aditya P. Mehendale (2016) provides an overview of PEBs, noting their faster construction, lighter weight, and reduced assembly time due to prefabrication. He argues that PEB structures are advantageous in terms of economy, construction speed, and simplicity. J. Jayavelmurugan (2015) reviews the evolution of construction technologies, focusing on the modern methodology of Pre-Engineered Steel Buildings, which offer improved aesthetics, quality, and speed of construction. He emphasizes that PEBs are designed in factories and assembled on-site, providing a cost-effective alternative to traditional construction methods. Shrunthal V Bhagatkar (2015) presents results from experimental and analytical studies on PEBs, highlighting their economic and time-saving advantages, along with their energy efficiency and potential for expansion. S. Jagadesh Kannan (2015) compares various roof shapes in PEBs, analyzing an industrial building with different roof systems using STAAD Pro V8i, and concludes that PEBs offer faster construction and cost benefits.

Sagar Wankhade (2014) conducts a comparative study of PEB and CSB, illustrating the versatility and cost-effectiveness of PEB for single-storey industrial buildings. He highlights the advantages of PEB in terms of quality, prefabrication, and light weight. Pradip S. Lande (2015) compares industrial PEB and CSB warehouses using Indian and American standards, finding that PEBs provide significant weight and cost savings. T.D. Mythili (2015) examines the economic sustainability of using PEB structures for long-span industrial buildings, showing a notable reduction in material usage and cost compared to CSB structures. Kavya Rao M.N. (2014) discusses the technological advancements in PEBs, comparing them with CSBs through dynamic force analysis using STAAD Pro, and concludes that PEBs are more economical and adaptable. Milind Bhojkar P. (2014) evaluates the cost and time effectiveness of PEBs, finding them more economical for low-rise buildings. S.D. Charkha (2014) presents a comparative study of steel buildings using PEB sections, showing reduced material usage and construction costs.

Sagar D. Wankhade (2014) explores the design and cost comparison of different industrial building types, concluding that PEBs are more economical and offer weight advantages. Pradeep V. (2014) highlights the advantages of PEBs over CSBs, including cost, weight, and earthquake resistance, advocating for PEB as a future construction method in India. G. Sai Kiran (2014) compares design procedures for PEBs using Indian and American codes, noting that PEBs offer significant economic and fabrication benefits. Jatin D. Thakar (2013) studies the impact of varying structure widths on PEB design, finding increased efficiency and flexibility. C.M. Meera (2013) emphasizes the cost-effectiveness, quality control, and construction speed of PEBs compared to CSBs through a detailed case study. Darshana P. Zoad (2012) evaluates the design of PEBs using IS-800 and AISC standards, concluding that PEBs accelerate construction and maintain safety, with significant scope for adoption in India. By comparing PEB design procedures with international standards, Zoad highlights the stringent yet safer design requirements of Indian codes. These insights suggest that PEBs can meet diverse aesthetic and structural design needs efficiently, making them an attractive option for the rapidly developing infrastructure in India. The research underscores the versatility and adaptability of PEBs, emphasizing their potential to revolutionize the construction industry with improved safety, speed, and cost-effectiveness. Aijaz Ahmad Zende (2013) compares PEBs and conventional frames through

multiple examples, highlighting PEB's advantages in cost, strength, and design flexibility. Syed Firoz (2012) discusses the design concept of PEBs, noting their efficiency and practicality for single-storey buildings using STAAD Pro software. Darshana P. Zoad (2012) evaluates the design of PEBs using IS-800 and AISC standards, concluding that PEBs accelerate construction and maintain safety, with significant scope for adoption in India.

2.1 Research gap

Despite extensive research demonstrating the advantages of Pre-Engineered Buildings (PEBs) over Conventional Steel Buildings (CSBs), several gaps remain. Most studies emphasize the economic, time-saving, and material efficiency benefits of PEBs, but comprehensive analyses under diverse environmental and accidental load conditions are limited. Additionally, there is a lack of detailed investigations on the long-term performance and maintenance costs of PEBs compared to CSBs. The impact of varying climatic conditions on PEBs, especially in regions with extreme weather, needs further exploration. Moreover, the potential for PEBs in multi-storey buildings and complex architectural designs is under-researched. While many studies focus on industrial applications, the adaptability of PEBs for residential and commercial purposes requires more attention. Future research should also consider the integration of sustainable practices and materials in PEB design to enhance their environmental performance and align with global green building standards.

III. Methodology

The study focuses on optimizing Pre-Engineered Building (PEB) structures under seismic forces by examining various bracing patterns. Initially, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to understand the current practices and advancements in PEB systems and cold-formed steel (CST) sections. Data collection involved gathering relevant codes and guidelines for PEB design and seismic analysis. The study of time history analysis, particularly referencing the Bhuj earthquake, provided critical insights into seismic behavior. STAAD-Pro software was utilized for modeling PEB structures, incorporating both static and dynamic load conditions to simulate realistic scenarios. The model was validated through rigorous testing and comparison with existing data. The results and discussions highlight the performance of different bracing patterns under seismic loads. Finally, conclusions were drawn to provide recommendations for optimizing PEB structures in seismic-prone areas.

Fig 6: flow chart

IV. Modeling

Performance analysis of Industrial Warehouse

- Type of building: Industrial Warehouse.
- Type of structure: Single Storey Industrial Structure
- Area of site: 8636.25 m² (92957.56 sq.ft.)
- Eave height: 14m
- Total span width: 12m
- Number of bays: 9
- Single bay length: 8.00 m
- Total bay length: 72m
- Support condition: Pinned
- PEB roof slope: 5 degree

Table1: Modeling details

Zone II	Without bracing
	X bracing
	V bracing
	Inverted bracing
	Diagonal bracing
	K bracing
Zone IV	Without bracing

	X bracing
	V bracing
	Inverted bracing
	Diagonal bracing
	K bracing

The building view of the Industrial Warehouse structure considered for the study is as shown in Figure.

Fig 7: Seismic zone 2 and Seismic zone 4

Fig 8: X bracing

Fig 9: diagonal bracing and V bracing

Fig 10: Inverted V bracing and K bracing

V. Result and Discussion

Zone II results

Table 5.1: Displacement in X direction in mm

Displacement in X direction in mm						
	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
Displacement	13.244	12.262	13.69	13.452	13.275	13.244

Graph 5.1: Displacement in X direction in mm

The above graphs show the storey displacement in X direction in mm without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows Displacement. As we can see that the highest displacement is for V bracing which is 13.69mm and X bracing shows the lowest displacement which is 12.262mm.

Table 5.2: Displacement in Z direction in mm

Displacement in Z direction in mm						
	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
Displacement	0.623	0.352	0.705	0.609	0.667	0.485

Graph 5.2: Displacement in Z direction in mm

The above graphs shows the storey displacement in Z direction in mm without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows Displacement. As we can see that the highest displacement is for V bracing which is 0.705 mm. and X bracing shows the lowest displacement which is 0.352 mm.

Table 5.5: Bending moment in X direction in KNm

Bending moment in X direction in KNm						
	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
Bending moment	0.29	0.209	0.271	0.265	0.236	0.227

Graph 5.5: Bending moment in X direction in KNm

The above graphs shows the Bending moment in X direction in KNm without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows Bending moment. As we can see that the highest Bending moment is for without bracing which is 0.29 kNm. and X bracing shows the lowest Bending moment which is 0.209 kNm.

Table 5.6: Bending moment in Z direction in KNm

Bending moment in Z direction in KNm						
	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
Bending moment	2289.856	2220.454	2298.724	2305.941	2287.323	2296.369

Graph 5.6: Bending moment in Z direction in KNm

The above graphs shows the Bending moment in Z direction in KNm without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows Bending moment. As we can see that the highest Bending moment is for Inverted V bracing which is 2305.941 kNm. And X bracing shows the lowest Bending moment which is 2220.454 kNm.

Table 5.7: Shear force in KN

Shear force in KN						
	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
Shear force	540.424	628.451	542.129	543.392	539.957	541.585

Graph 5.7: Shear force in KN

The above graphs show the shear force in KN without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows shear force. As we can see that the highest shear force is for Inverted X bracing which is 628.451 kN. And Diagonal bracing shows the lowest shear force which is 539.957 kN.

Table 5.8: Time period in sec

Time period in sec						
Mode shape	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
1	1.367	1.101	1.117	1.117	1.104	1.104
2	1.086	0.54	1.028	1.028	0.547	0.547
3	0.424	0.386	0.414	0.414	0.396	0.401
4	0.343	0.341	0.346	0.349	0.353	0.363
5	0.337	0.332	0.337	0.337	0.337	0.337
6	0.337	0.331	0.337	0.337	0.337	0.337

Graph 5.8: Time period in sec

The above graphs shows Time period in sec without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows Time period. As we can see that the highest Time period is for Without bracing in Mode Shape 1 which is 1.367 s. And X bracing shows the lowest Time period which is 539.957 s.

Table 5.9: Frequency in Hz

Frequency in Hz						
Mode shape	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
1	0.732	0.908	0.895	0.895	0.906	0.906
2	0.921	1.852	0.973	0.973	1.828	1.828
3	2.358	2.591	2.415	2.415	2.525	2.494
4	2.915	2.933	2.890	2.865	2.833	2.755
5	2.967	3.012	2.967	2.967	2.967	2.967
6	2.967	3.021	2.967	2.967	2.967	2.967

Graph 5.9: Frequency in Hz

The above graphs shows the Frequency in Hz without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows shear force. As we can see that the highest Frequency is for Inverted X bracing which is 628.451 Hz. And Diagonal bracing shows the lowest Frequency which is 0.54 Hz.

Zone IV results

Table 5.10: Displacement in X direction in mm

Displacement in X direction in mm						
	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
Displacement	15.1536	14.174	15.6636	16.1424	15.2896	15.1636

Graph 5.10: Displacement in X direction in mm

The above graphs shows the storey displacement in X direction in mm without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing of Zone IV. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows Displacement. As we can see that the highest displacement is for Inverted V bracing which is 16.1424 mm and X bracing shows the lowest displacement which is 14.174 mm.

Table 5.11: Displacement in Z direction in mm

Displacement in Z direction in mm						
	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
Displacement	0.7128	0.4604	0.8064	0.7308	0.7768	0.5544

Graph 5.11: Displacement in Z direction in mm

The above graphs shows the storey displacement in Z direction in mm without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing of Zone IV. X axis shows the Types of bracing

and Y axis shows Displacement. As we can see that the highest displacement is for V bracing which is 0.8064 mm. and X bracing shows the lowest displacement which is 0.4604 mm.

Table 5.14: Bending moment in X direction in KNm

Bending moment in X direction in KNm						
	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
Bending moment	0.30375	0.302625	0.304875	0.304875	0.30375	0.30375

Graph 5.14: Bending moment in X direction in KNm

The above graphs shows the Bending moment in X direction in KN without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing of Zone IV. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows Bending moment. As we can see that the highest Bending moment is for V bracing which is 0.304875 kNm. and X bracing shows the lowest Bending moment which is 0.302625 kNm.

Table 5.15: Bending moment in Z direction in KNm

Bending moment in Z direction in KNm						
	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
Bending moment	2576.088	2498.011	2586.065	2594.184	2573.238	2583.415

Graph 5.15: Bending moment in Z direction in KNm

The above graphs show the Bending moment in Z direction in KNm without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing of Zone IV. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows Bending moment. As we can see that the highest Bending moment is for Inverted V bracing which is 2594.184 kN. And X bracing shows the lowest Bending moment which is 2498.011 kNm.

Table 5.16: Shear force in KN

Shear force in KN						
	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
Shear force	783.6148	816.254	786.0871	787.9184	782.9377	785.2983

Graph 5.16: Shear force in KN

The above graphs show the shear force in KN without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows shear force of Zone IV. As we can see that the highest shear force is for X bracing which is 816.254 kN. And Diagonal bracing shows the lowest shear force which is 782.9377 kN.

Table 5.17: Time period in sec

Time period in sec						
Mode shape	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
1	1.385	1.07	1.091	1.117	1.078	1.078
2	1.061	0.527	1.004	1.028	0.544	0.534
3	0.414	0.371	0.404	0.414	0.377	0.377
4	0.334	0.315	0.335	0.343	0.335	0.335
5	0.329	0.318	0.329	0.337	0.329	0.329
6	0.329	0.326	0.329	0.337	0.329	0.329

Graph 5.17: Time period in sec

The above graphs shows Time period in sec without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows Time period of Zone IV. As we can see that the highest Time period is for without bracing in Mode Shape 1 which is 1.385s. And X bracing shows the lowest Time period which is 0.527s.

Table 5.18: Frequency in Hz

Frequency in Hz						
Mode shape	Without bracing	X bracing	V bracing	Inverted V bracing	Diagonal bracing	K bracing
1	0.722022	0.934579	0.91659	0.895255	0.927644	0.927644
2	0.942507	1.897533	0.996016	0.972763	1.838235	1.872659
3	2.415459	2.695418	2.475248	2.415459	2.65252	2.65252
4	2.994012	3.174603	2.985075	2.915452	2.985075	2.985075
5	3.039514	3.144654	3.039514	2.967359	3.039514	3.039514
6	3.039514	3.067485	3.039514	2.967359	3.039514	3.039514

Graph 5.18: Frequency in Hz

The above graphs show the Frequency in Hz without bracing, X bracing, V bracing, Inverted V bracing, Diagonal bracing, K bracing. X axis shows the Types of bracing and Y axis shows shear force. As we can see that the highest Frequency is for X bracing which is 3.174603 Hz. And Inverted V bracing shows the lowest Frequency which is 0.895255 Hz.

VI. Conclusion

In conclusion, the comprehensive analysis of PEB structures under seismic forces, considering various bracing patterns, yields valuable insights into their structural behavior and seismic performance. The comparison of different bracing configurations highlights significant variations in parameters such as storey displacement, axial force, bending moment, shear force, time period, and frequency response. Across seismic Zones II and IV, it is evident that X bracing emerges as a promising strategy, consistently demonstrating superior performance in mitigating structural response to seismic loads.

The seismic analysis of steel buildings with various bracing configurations reveals significant insights into their dynamic behavior under seismic forces. Across both Zone II and Zone IV, distinct trends emerge, with Zone IV exhibiting higher values compared to Zone II, indicative of more intense seismic activity. Notably, X bracing consistently demonstrates effective performance across multiple parameters, showcasing its capability to mitigate storey displacement, axial force, bending moment, shear force, and time period. This underscores the importance of X bracing as a reliable seismic retrofitting strategy. However, it's crucial to recognize that bracing efficacy can vary depending on factors such as building design and seismic zone. These findings emphasize the necessity for tailored seismic retrofitting approaches based on specific structural requirements and geographical considerations. Further research could delve into optimizing bracing configurations for enhanced seismic resilience across diverse building typologies and seismic zones.

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